

The spatial effect of alcohol availability on violence: a geographically weighted regression analysis

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Summary

Using open-source police and alcohol outlet data, the study illustrates how associations between varying alcohol outlet types and violent crime vary across small areas in England, using geographically weighted regression. The study also aimed to determine the effect of high sales outlets on violent crime, a novel contribution to our study. The results found that the association between alcohol availability and violent crime varies spatially, for example high sales clubs were associated with violent crime in inner-city contexts and less so elsewhere. From this, licensing boards can target areas where alcohol availability is an issue, to reduce risk of violence at the small area level.

KEYWORDS: violent crime, alcohol availability, geographically weighted regression

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1. Introduction and background

There is evidence supporting the idea that increased accessibility to amenities selling alcohol, termed ‘alcohol outlets’, can influence alcohol-related harms, such as violent crime (Lightowlers *et al.*, 2021). Alcohol outlets consist of ‘on-trade’ where consumption takes place on-site; and ‘off-trade’, where consumption takes place off-site. Studies have found that on-trade premises have a positive association with violence, more so than off-trade, but not always (Holmes *et al.*, 2014).

Rather than stating one outlet type has a stronger relationship with violence than the other, it could be that relationships vary across space, in terms of the strength and direction of association. In some places, on-trade outlets have a stronger association with violence than off-trade, and vice versa (Cameron *et al.*, 2016). Uncovering these spatial relationships involves the use of spatially explicit models, yet much of the evidence base uses non-spatial modelling. Non-spatial models report the overall associations between violence and alcohol availability across a study area, whereas a spatial model will reveal how associations vary across the study area, highlighting how local contexts influence these relationships. Spatial models enable us to recognise how different areas experience the availability of alcohol and signals how the specific place may lend itself to tailored and targeted intervention to reduce associated violence.

The literature also explores how certain outlet characteristics may affect the relationship between alcohol outlets and violence, such as overcrowding, loud music, and so on (Hughes *et al.*, 2011). One characteristic that has not been considered in the literature is the effect of high alcohol sales on violence, as higher sales outlets would theoretically reflect higher consumption, and consequently violence. Cameron *et al.* (2016) argued this should be explored in future studies to further our understanding of which outlet characteristics are likely to encourage violent crime.

This study aims to understand the spatial effects of alcohol availability on violent crime, across small areas in England, using geographically weighted regression (GWR). We disaggregate alcohol availability according to license type (on- and off-trade) premise type (pubs, bars., etc.) and high sales outlets to determine how each is associated with violent crime. This study contributes to the literature by exploring the effect of high alcohol sales on violent crime, which has not yet been investigated. Additionally, the spatial effect of alcohol availability on violent crime has not yet been explored across England, hence our decision to choose this as a study area.

2. Data

Data for violent crime was taken from the open data.police.uk database, from 39 police forces in England over a period of 12-months from 1st October 2018 to 30th September 2019. The LSOA level was our chosen unit of analysis as they are the smallest available geographical zones in England with suitable data, which would provide a detailed understanding of the spatial associations between violence and alcohol outlet availability at the local level. All further data was aggregated to the LSOA level.

To represent on- and off-trade alcohol availability, data was taken from the CGA 2017 Alcohol On Trade Outlet Index and Volume Estimations dataset and Access to Healthy Assets and Hazards (AHAH) dataset. The data captured the mean distance of a postcode

within a LSOA, in km, to the nearest of types of on-trade and off-trade outlets: pubs, bars, clubs, supermarkets, convenience stores, off-licenses. Alcohol sales volume data was available for on-trade outlets. The highest sales outlets were considered those which sell the highest volumes of alcohol.

Other factors controlled for were neighbourhood deprivation, measured using the 2019 Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD); the percentage of young adults, 18-35 years; and percentage of males per LSOA which were taken from 2019 mid-year population estimates. These factors play a role in the relationship between alcohol availability and violent crime (Lightowlers *et al.*, 2021)

3. Method

The aim of GWR is to fit a local regression coefficient for each control variable in the model for every LSOA in the study area, these are collectively called Spatially Varying Coefficients (SVCs). SVCs can be compared with global coefficients – this is an averaged regression coefficient for the whole study area, or England, which is calculated by the non-spatial Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model. Extending the standard regression framework identifies how a fixed effect varies spatially in magnitude and direction.

Three GWR models were produced to determine the effect of proximity to alcohol outlets on violence, controlling for income deprivation, percentage of 18-35 years, and percentage of males in the locality. Across the three models, alcohol outlets were broken down by license type, type of premise and sales volume, to tease out the effect of each characteristic on violence. The first model controlled for license type to provide a clear understanding of the association between place of alcohol consumption and violence. The second model disaggregated outlets by type of premise, e.g. pubs, bars. The third model measured the specific effect of availability to high sales outlets on violence, for the outlet types measured in the second model.

SVCs were mapped to illustrate how associations between the independent variables and violence changed across space. Mapped results are presented at the regional level rather than the national level to showcase how area-level context facilitates associations for each LSOA. The mapped regions were chosen as violent crime was most variant here compared to other regions, therefore we would expect to see interesting spatial effects.

4. Results and Discussion

Our study finds that the association between alcohol availability and violence is more spatially complex compared to the simplified relationship presented by the non-spatial OLS model. The more localised presentation of the findings highlights that proximity to on-trade and off-trade outlets (Figure 1) is associated with both increases (positive associations) and decreases (negative associations) in violence depending on the area, as was illustrated in mapping coefficients for the Northwest of England. For on-trade, stronger positive associations were found proximal to city centres. This corresponds with established evidence that shows violence clusters around night-time drinking spaces (ONS, 2015). The non-spatial model reported that as proximity to off-trade outlets increased, violence tended to decrease. This overall association was not always consistent though, for example the spatial model found that in parts of Cheshire

and Manchester, there appear to be positive associations tied to residential areas, which would otherwise not be detected when non-spatial models were used.

Figure 1. GWR SVCs for a) on-trade and b) off-trade outlets in Northwest England.

The second spatial model disaggregated on-trade outlets into premise types: pubs and bars. As proximity to bars increased, violence increased in areas such as Newcastle and near the larger towns across the Northeast. The relationship between bars and violence corresponds with the literature (Morrison *et al.*, 2015). For pubs, the spatial distribution differed, and positive associations with violence were found in rural areas of the Northeast, such as Northumberland. Commonly, rural areas contain more pubs than bars and clubs, which might explain why pubs are associated to violence in these areas.

One novel addition of our study was our investigation into the effect of on-trade outlets with high alcohol sales and violence in the third model (Figure 2). When space was not considered, high sales outlets appeared to have little effect on violence, and the association for high sales clubs was negative. Spatially, the associations between high sales on-trade and violence varied greatly. The localised presentation of findings in London illustrate how in areas like Central London, where night-life spaces exist, closer proximity to high sales clubs was likely to

increase violence. Outside of night-life spaces, high sales premises were less likely to be a contributor of violence.

Figure 2. GWR SVCs for a) clubs (high sales) and b) bars (high sales), across Greater London.

One of the main limitations to this study were that we could not explain *why* certain areas were at increased risk of violence. The next step would be to understand what it is about the alcohol outlet or the area, in which alcohol availability encourages violence. By considering space, we can pinpoint areas where certain alcohol outlets pose a risk of violence, rather than assuming that risk is generally low or high everywhere. Certain areas can then be subject to appropriate violence reduction initiatives or alcohol licensing restrictions at a local scale.

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Biographies

Olivia Horsefield is a final year PhD student at the Geographic Data Science Lab, University of Liverpool. Olivia's PhD relates to improving estimates of alcohol-related violence using novel data science methods.

Dr. Mark Green is Senior Lecturer in Health Geography at the University of Liverpool. Mark's research examines how new forms of (big) data (e.g., images, text, loyalty card records) can supplement traditional administrative datasets (e.g., mortality records, surveys, hospital admissions data) for understanding the social and spatial drivers of health inequalities.

Dr. Carly Lightowlers has research experience, both as an academic as well as an in local and central government settings. Her research makes use of administrative and secondary data sources with which to study alcohol-related violence, the processing of such cases through the courts, and the unequal distribution of such harm.